

NEIL FLEMING ON LEARNING STYLES

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Abstract. Neil Fleming and Colin Mills proposed the VARK model, which identifies four types of learning preferences: Visual, Aural, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic. This model has become popular in the educational environment and is used to develop teaching materials that take into account different types of people.

Key words: learning styles, Neil Fleming, VARK model, information perception, multimodal method.

НИЛ ФЛЕМИНГ О СТИЛЯХ ОБУЧЕНИЯ

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Нил Флеминг и Колин Миллс предложили модель VARK, которая выделяет четыре типа предпочтений в обучении: визуальный, аудиальный, чтение/письмо и кинестетический. Эта модель стала популярной в образовательной среде и используется для разработки учебных материалов, учитывающих различные типы людей.

Ключевые слова: стили обучения, Нил Флеминг, модель VARK, восприятие информации, мультимодальный способ.

NIL FLEMING O'QITISH USLUBLARI HAQIDA

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Nil Fleming va Kolin Mills VARK modelini taklif qildilar, u o'rganishning to'rtta turini aniqlaydi: vizual, eshitish, o'qish/yo'zish va kinestetik. Ushbu model ta'lim muhitida mashhur bo'lib, har xil turdagi odamlarni hisobga olgan holda o'quv materiallarini ishlab chiqishda qo'llaniladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qitish uslublari, Nil Fleming, VARK modeli, axborotni idrok qilish, multimodal usul.

Introduction. Teachers have always been trying to help their students to study better. They use different methods and ways to make the learning process easier and more beneficial for the students. I have heard about VARK classification only in 2023. I find the idea of defining what kind of learner each student is very important and useful. I am sure it will help to improve the process of teaching and learning English.

Learning styles is a term generally used to describe an individual's natural or habitual pattern of acquiring and processing information in [learning](#) situations. There is no commonly accepted definition of learning styles; however, a core concept is that individuals differ in how they learn. The idea of individualized "learning styles" originated in the 1970s, and acquired "enormous popularity".

One of the most common and widely-used categorizations of the various types of learning styles is Fleming's VARK model (sometimes VAK) which expanded upon earlier [Neuro-linguistic programming \(VARK\)](#) models:

1. [visual learners](#);

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2. [auditory learners](#);
3. [kinesthetic learners](#) or [tactile learners](#)

Literature review. Neil Fleming and his colleagues in a number of works revealed the essence of the VARK model and learning styles [1; 2]. L. Volodina in her article provides methods for determining the type of perception and gives them a brief description [3]. E. Shumova and Z. Mirzaeva paid attention to three types of language learning: visual, auditory and kinesthetic [6; 7]. The question of the effectiveness of using the VARK model was revealed by a number of foreign scientists who conducted research, surveys, tests among students and teachers [5].

Discussion and results. Fleming claimed that visual learners have a preference for seeing (think in pictures; visual aids such as overhead slides, diagrams, handouts, etc.). Auditory learners best learn through listening (lectures, discussions, tapes, etc.). Tactile/kinesthetic learners prefer to learn via experience - moving, touching, and doing (active exploration of the world; science projects; experiments, etc.). Its use in pedagogy allows teachers to prepare classes that address each of these areas. Students can also use the model to identify their preferred learning style and maximize their educational experience by focusing on what benefits them the most [1].

Neil Fleming has been learning about teaching and learning for forty years. His full time teaching was divided between secondary, teacher education and university (Lincoln University, New Zealand) with ample recognition of his teaching and research prowess in those three sectors. For the past ten years he has been facilitating active workshops on a variety of topics in North America, Asia and Europe travelling there in spring and fall. He has been the main author of the VARK books available online. Recently he has been in demand for work with customer service applications of the VARK principles in business environments. He has also been working with elite sports coaches on a learning-preferences approach to coaching. Apart from managing the interesting contacts with the VARK website he has frequent grandchildren duties, volunteers a day each week at a low decile primary school, tends his collection of 80 heritage roses and makes solid wood furniture as a hobby.

VARK tells you something about yourself that you may or may not know. It can be used to understand your boss, your colleagues, your parents, your workmates, your partner, your customers, your teacher, your relatives, your clients and yourself. It is a short, simple inventory that has been well-received because its dimensions are intuitively understood and its applications are practical. It has helped people understand each other and assists them to learn more effectively in many situations [1].

Although copyrighted and trademarked for business use, VARK is free for use in colleges, high schools, and universities for student or faculty development as long as attribution is given.

Although we have known for centuries about the different modes, this inventory, initially developed in 1987 by Neil Fleming, Christchurch, New Zealand, was the first to systematically present a series of questions with helpsheets for students, teachers, employees, customers, suppliers and others to use in their own way. Many inventories label people who then want to ask "*So what?*" VARK goes on to provide strategies that help people understand and move on from any label. Once you know about VARK, its power to explain things will be a revelation.

The principal creator of the VARK learning styles model, Neil Fleming, wrote: "I was surprised that some excellent teachers could not reach certain students, while other, less experienced teachers were successful". Fleming based his model on the Barb model, dividing the visual type into text (Reading/writing) and symbolic (Visual). The teacher also relied on developments, his own observations and conversations with students and teachers. According to Fleming's theory, students

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can have more than one dominant learning style. In one of his articles, he cited the following statistics from online testing: 41% of those who took the test have one dominant learning style; 27% have two styles; 9% have three styles and as many as 21% of those tested have a focus in all four styles. Fleming and colleagues call the tendency to more than one style multimodality [4].

Based on the research of Neil Fleming, a theory of four-channel perception of information emerged. According to this theory, a person perceives the world with the help of several senses, but only one of them dominates. For better assimilation of the material, it is necessary to combine different types of tasks, different methods of presenting the material and different methods of control (for example, tests or classic tests, or teach not only verbally, but also visually).

Conclusion. Currently, one of the potential alternatives to classical models of learning styles may be a multimodal method that combines all learning styles VARK. This method involves relying on different types of perception: when explaining, you can see a picture, listen to the information and read it, just as we do when watching videos on social networks. Neil Fleming outlines the basic principles of his model:

Preferred styles influence people's behavior, including learning.

Learning styles are not fixed, but they are stable in the medium term.

Both students and teachers can reliably identify and provide examples of how their preferred style is used in learning and teaching.

Preferences can be compared to learning strategies. There are learning strategies that are better suited to some styles than others. Using your weakest styles to learn is useless; so is using other students' preferred styles.

Information that is accessed using strategies that match the learner's preferred learning styles is more likely to be understood and motivated.

Using study strategies that match your learning style is also likely to give you the impetus to study harder, learn more deeply, and engage in active and effective metacognition.

Knowing and acting on your learning style is an important prerequisite for improving your learning.

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